

ASSEMBLAGE AND MICROHABITATS OF ANURANS FROM MT. SINAKA, ARAKAN, COTABATO AND MT. HAMIGUITAN, DAVAO ORIENTAL, MINDANAO ISLAND, PHILIPPINES

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ABSTRACT – Documentation of species composition, richness and microhabitat preferences of anurans of two mountain ranges: Mt. Sinaka (Arakan Cotabato) and Mt. Hamiguitan (Davao, Oriental) was done using belt transect sampling. Twenty-three species were recorded representing five anuran families. Nineteen species were recorded for Mt. Sinaka while 14 species were accounted from Mt. Hamiguitan. Sixty one percent of the species are endemic and eight of the species documented are threatened. Only two species were documented on all sampling sites. Overlaps in the use of various microhabitats were observed although many species were documented on ground microhabitats. Considering all of these, the need to conserve habitats of all types is therefore deemed a necessity.

Keywords: belt transect walks, richness, endemic, microhabitat preferences

INTRODUCTION

Amphibians thrive in a variety of habitats, ranging from relatively pristine sites in forested areas to areas close to anthropogenic activities including water puddles, ditches, canals near houses and rice fields (International Union for the Conservation of Nature Global Amphibian Assessment 2004; Inger 1954; Alcalá and Brown 1998). Various studies attest that each amphibian species occupy certain habitat type, some species are highly confined to forested areas while others are easily sighted near human domiciles. For instance, the species of the genus *Platymantis* were reported to inhabit closed-canopy forest (Alcalá and Brown 1998) while the *Fejervarya* species were likely to be sampled in canals and ditches near human settlements and in flooded rice fields (Inger 1954; Diesmos *et al.* 2003).

The variability of habitats utilized by amphibian species is greatly influenced by their physiological needs. Due to their cutaneous respiration, a diet composed mainly of insects, the non-direct development of the young (for the majority of Philippine frogs), the need for a humid environment, water bodies and vegetation is quite necessary (Sexton *et al.* 1964). Forest dwellers were observed in closed canopy areas, relatively wet forest floor, moderately thick leaf litter and quite humid sites. Still others were found in clean water bodies in the forest interior or near banks of these bodies where vegetation is abundant. Burrowing species on the other hand, occupy prop roots and even decaying logs.

Another factor that directs habitat preferences of amphibians is disturbance. Majority of the Philippine frog species were documented on less disturbed or undisturbed sites (Alcalá 1986; Alcalá and Brown

1998; Diesmos *et al.* 2003; Brown *et al.* 1996).

Notes on microhabitats of amphibians abound (Brown *et al.* 1996; Brown *et al.* 2000; Brown and Alcalá 1994; Gaulke, 1994b). However, presentations on microhabitats of species sampled from various mountain ranges are quite rare. It is on this ground that this paper is premised. Further, information regarding microhabitat preferences of select frog species is also presented.

METHODS

Samples for this study were collected in separate mountain ranges: Mt. Sinaka in Arakan, Cotabato, Central Mindanao and Mt. Hamiguitan in San Isidro, Eastern Mindanao (Figure 1). Descriptions of the sampling sites are given below:

Mt. Sinaka Sampling Sites:

1. So. Sinai, Brgy Salasang (7°22'25.7" N, 125°12'47.7"E). Approximately 870 - 1425 masl, this site covers three habitat types: dipterocarp, montane and mossy forest. The areas of lowland forest though are vast tracts of grasslands, mostly converted to agricultural lands. Diameters at breast heights of trees were 30 - 160 cm (canopy trees) and 100 - 250 cm for emergent trees. The height of the trees is between 5 - 20 m (canopy) reaching up to 35 m for emergent trees. Tree species observed include red and white Lauan, marobo, anagdong, alom-alom, tanguile, nato, catmon, cinnamon, ulayan, mountain agoho, tinikaran (*Leptospermum* sp.) and sagimsim. Rotting logs and small streams are abundant in this area especially as one approaches the forest interior. Leaf litter is thick and forest floor wet. Sampling was done from 30 July to August 8, 2004.

2. So. Napunungan, Brgy Tumanding (7°21'48" N, 125°12'59.9"E). This site encompasses dipterocarp,

montane and mossy forests between elevations of 950 – 1430 masl. The terrain is relatively steeper than that of Barangay Salasang. Diameter at breast height of trees is between 30 – 95 cm (canopy) and 0.6 - 190 cm (emergent) while the height of the trees fall between 6 - 20 m (canopy) and up to 30 m for emergent trees. *Ficus* sp., *Musa* sp. and *Pandanus* sp. are prominent in the site. Further, leaf litter thickness and wetness of the forest floor increase as one goes towards the forest interior. Fieldwork was conducted from 16 to 25 October 2004.

Mt. Hamiguitan Sampling Sites

1. Sitio Tumulite (N 06° 44' 3.4", E 126° 09' 3.4"). The area is an upper dipterocarp forest with an elevation of 545 – 785 masl. The sampling site is dominated by "Malabayabas" having a DBH range of 6 - 86 cm and a relatively sloping terrain. The forest floor has a thick layer of dry leaf litter with tree stumps and abundant rotting logs; streams and creeks are present (both dried-up and active). Habitat disturbance is observed as selective logging done in the past and more recently slash and burn agriculture. The sampling plot is outside the proclaimed wildlife sanctuary and is part of a Community Based Forest Management site (CBFM). It is accessible by a 3-4 hour hike through a jungle trail from the nearest community. Sampling was conducted from 16 – 24 May 2005.

2. Tinagong Dagat (N 6° 43' 56", E 126° 10' 41"). The site is a transitional montane-mossy forest with an elevation of 950 -1,200 masl. Vegetation is dominated by species belonging to the Families *Podocarpaceae* (*Dacrydium elatum*), *Sapotaceae* (*Palaquium* sp.), *Araucareaceae* (*Agathis philippinensis* or *Almaciga*) and *Myrtaceae* (*Syzigium* sp). Climbing vines such as *Freycinetia* sp., tree ferns and pitcher plants are abundant and *Medinilla* sp. Are observed to be fruiting. The forest floor has a thick leaf litter with a substrate consisting of a layer of humus. The sampling plot is accessible by a ca. 6 hour hike through a jungle trail that passes the Alog river from So. Magum. Sampling was made from 18 – 29 July 2005.

Sampling Method

Different sampling methods were employed in the sites. For the Sinaka sampling sites, a modified belt transect survey (Heyer *et al.* 1994) was used. The two kilometer transect established for birds placed on existing foot trails was also used as the belt transect for anuran sampling. For the Hamiguitan area, belt transect walks on ten-100 m long transects per site were surveyed. In both methods, a team of three people searched for amphibians along the two-kilometer transect. Transects were visited twice daily (diurnal and nocturnal). Sampling was also done on both sides of the transect five meters each. Searches on tree holes, buttresses and water bodies located within and outside transects, were also made. Walks were conducted between 0900-1400 hours and from 1800 – 2100 h. For the nocturnal walks, headlamps,

flashlights and torches were used. Representative samples of all species were collected as voucher specimens while the rest were released after identification. Ideally individuals for release must be marked using methods such as toe clipping and fluorescent dyeing (Bennett 1999). However, methods for marking individuals for release were not used and thus there is no way of ensuring that similar individuals were recaptured. Samples were initially preserved in 10% formalin in the field and were later transferred to 70% ethanol for storage. For species identification, amphibian guides by Alcala and Brown (1998), Frost (2004) and Inger (1954) were used. Specimens were deposited at the University of the Philippines in Mindanao and the Philippine National Museum.

Microhabitat Classification

Microhabitats refer to the location where samples were first sighted. Three broad categories were made: arboreal, ground and aquatic. Arboreal habitats refer to those elevated from the ground (5 – 10 m) including branches and stems of plants, leaves and leaf axils. Ground microhabitats refer to microhabitats directly on the ground (0 – 5 m), or on rotting logs and tree buttresses. Lastly, the aquatic microhabitats include streams, rivers, and creeks as well as standing bodies of water.

Figure 1. Map of Mindanao Island showing prominent mountain ranges, Hamiguitan and Sinaka.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Species Composition and Richness

Twenty three species were documented in all of the sites representing five anuran families. Nineteen species were recorded in Mt. Sinaka and 14 species were recorded for Mt. Hamiguitan. (Table 1). Sixty one percent (14 species) of the total were endemics, 10 are confined to the Mindanao Faunal Region. Eight of the species documented are threatened. Two species, *Megophrys stejnegeri* and *Rana grandocula* were found common on all of the sites.

Table 1. The list of species encountered in each of the four sites. Endemism: P – Philippine Endemic, M – Mindanao Faunal Region Endemic; Diel Activity: D – diurnal; N – Nocturnal. Status conforms with CITES, 2006 (<http://www.cites.org>), IUCN Red List, 2006 (<http://www.redlist.org>) and Global Amphibian Assessment (globalamphibiansassessment.org).

SPECIES	THREAT STATUS	MT. SINAKA SAMPLING SITES		MT. HAMIGUITAN SAMPLING SITES	
		Sinai (870 – 1425)	Napunangan (950 – 1430)	Palo X (545 – 785)	Tinagong Dagat (950 -1,200)
BUFONIDAE					
<i>Ansonia muelleri</i> M	Vulnerable	√		√	
<i>Pelophryne brevipes</i>		√	√		
<i>Pelophryne lighti</i> M	Vulnerable	√			
MEGOPHRYIDAE					
<i>Megophrys stejneri</i> M	Vulnerable	√	√	√	√
<i>Leptobrachium</i> sp.				√	
MICROHYLIDAE					
<i>Chaperina fusca</i>		√			
<i>Kalophrynus pleurostigma</i>		√	√		
RANIDAE					
<i>Fejervarya limnocharis</i>		√			
<i>Limnonectes leytenis</i> P			√		
<i>Limnonectes parvus</i> M	Vulnerable		√		
<i>Limnonectes cf diuatus</i>				√	
<i>Limnonectes magnus</i> M	Near Threatened			√	
<i>Platymantis corrugata</i> P		√	√	√	
<i>Platymantis guentheri</i> M	Vulnerable	√	√		√
<i>Rana everetti</i> P		√	√		√
<i>Rana grandocula</i> M		√	√	√	√
<i>Starois natator</i>			√	√	
RHACOPHORIDAE					
<i>Nyctixalus spinosus</i> M	Vulnerable	√	√		
<i>Philautus acutirostris</i> M	Vulnerable	√	√		√
<i>Philautus worcesteri</i> M	Vulnerable	√			
<i>Philautus surdus</i> P			√		√
<i>Philautus cf poecilus</i>					√
<i>Polypedates leucomystax</i>		√		√	√

Microhabitat Preferences

All microhabitat types were represented in all our sampling sites (Table 2). Majority of the species encountered were recorded on ground microhabitats including forest duff, leaf litter and interior of prop roots, inside or adjacent to rotting logs. Records of arboreal microhabitat in this study are attachment of the individuals to any foliage: fern, leaf axils of tree leaves or dried branch. Arboreal microhabitats also include detection of the species between the interior of branches that crossed. However, no incidence of encountering an individual inside a tree hole was recorded. For the aquatic microhabitats, samples were found near bodies of water such as streams, rivers or simply near standing pools of water. Other samples were also found attached on low lying

vegetation on the banks of these water bodies. Colored plates of representative microhabitats are given as Figure 2.

Differences in microhabitats occupied by some species were also observed. Two of the species found to the two mountains: *Ansonia muelleri* and *Platymantis guentheri* were encountered in two differing microhabitats. *A. muelleri* was documented on ground microhabitats in Mt. Sinaka while it was documented on a riparian microhabitat in Mt. Hamiguitan. *P. guentheri* was found in a ground microhabitat in Mt. Sinaka while it was recorded in an arboreal microhabitat in Mt. Hamiguitan.

Also prominent in the results are the disparities between species occupying similar microhabitat categories. For instance, *Rana grandocula* was

sampled on aquatic microhabitat on both sites on different areas: atop vegetation on stream bank (Mt. Sinaka) and on stream bank (Mt. Hamiguitan). Another instance is *Rana everetti* sampled in stream bank with free flowing water (Mt. Sinaka) while it was encountered in a standing pool of water in Mt. Hamiguitan.

The Philippines is currently noted as one of the herpetofaunal centers in the world having high species diversity and increased percentage of endemism (Brown *et al.* 2001; Diesmos *et al.* 2002). The presented data may likely attest to this statement, even if figures appear small on macro scale (Table 1). But considering that our data covers only portions of two mountain ranges in Mindanao, our assumption may be supported with our data especially for frogs.

In addition, data presented highlights frog species found in formerly unexplored mountains, Sinaka and Hamiguitan.

The disparity in the total number of species encountered per mountain can be considered a product of site differences in terms of geographic location and habitat types which consequently affected the following: number of available water bodies for breeding, leaf litter/forest ground conditions and over-all weather conditions. Mt. Sinaka is located near Central Mindanao whereas Hamiguitan is situated in Eastern Mindanao. Further, Mt. Hamiguitan differs from Mt. Sinaka in that it has an ultramafic soil condition characterized by stunted growth of plants. Based on Philippine Atmospheric

Table 2. The list of species encountered in each of the four sites. Endemism: P – Philippine Endemic, M–Mindanao Faunal Region Endemic; Microhabitats: G – ground, A – Arboreal, Aq – Aquatic.

SPECIES	MT. SINAKA		MT. HAMIGUITAN	
	Sinai (870 – 1425)	Napunangan (950 – 1430)	Tumalite (545 – 785)	Tinagong Dagat (950 -1,200)
BUFONIDAE				
<i>Ansonia muelleri</i> M	G		Aq	
<i>Pelophryne brevipes</i>	A	A		
<i>Pelophryne lighti</i> M	A			
MEGOPHRYIDAE				
<i>Megophrys stejneri</i> M	G	G	G	G
<i>Leptobrachium</i> sp.			G	
MICROHYLIDAE				
<i>Chaperina fusca</i>	G			
<i>Kalophrynus pleurostigma</i>	G	G		
RANIDAE				
<i>Fejervarya limnocharis</i>	Aq			
<i>Limnonectes leytensis</i> P		Aq		
<i>Limnonectes parvus</i> M		G		
<i>Limnonectes cf diuatus</i>			Aq	
<i>Limnonectes magnus</i>			Aq	
<i>Platymantis corrugata</i> P	G	G	G	
<i>Platymantis guentheri</i> M	G	G		A
<i>Rana everetti</i> P	Aq	A		Aq
<i>Rana grandocula</i> M	Aq	Aq	Aq	Aq
<i>Starois natator</i>		Aq	Aq	
RHACOPHORIDAE				
<i>Nyctixalus spinosus</i> M	A	A		
<i>Philautus acutirostris</i> M	A	A		A
<i>Philautus worcesteri</i> M	G			
<i>Philautus surdus</i> P		A		A
<i>Philautus cf poecilus</i>				A
<i>Polypedates leucomystax</i>	A		A	A
Total no of species	15	13	9	8
	G = 7	G = 5	G = 3	G = 1
	A = 5	A = 5	A = 1	A = 5
	Aq = 3	Aq = 3	Aq = 5	Aq = 2

Figure 2. The representative microhabitats to which samples were taken (top-bottom: ground, arboreal and aquatic). Ground - heap of leaf litter where *Megophrys stejnegeri* and *Ansonia muelleri* were found; Arboreal - leaf axils of trees where *Philautus acutirostris*, *P. surdus* and *Pelophryne lighti* were recorded; Aquatic - river with free flowing water, a riparian microhabitat which cradles *Rana grandocula*, *Limnectes magnus* and *Starois natator*.

Geophysical and Astronomical Services Administration climate classification, rain fall pattern also varies in each site. Mt. Sinaka has Type IV climate where rainfall is generally evenly distributed throughout the year with May and June as the monsoon months while Mt. Hamiguitan exhibits Type II climate with no dry season and only a

very pronounced rainy season from November to January with an average rainfall of 1,500-2,500 mm. This variable likely affects humidity as well as forest floor conditions in each sites.

The absence of some species which should be encountered in likely similar sites (Sinai and Palo X; Napunangan and Tinagong Dagat) are believed to be due to either one of the following reasons: samples were missed especially if individual samples are found in a heap of leaf litter, a very good camouflage; diminutive; and if species are site-specific endemic. The absence of *Pelophryne* species in Mt. Hamiguitan may be attributed to its minute size. Perhaps this species is also present in Mt. Hamiguitan but was missed during the sampling. Their minute size allowing them to easily appear as a small part of a stick or a portion of a leaf may have deceived the searcher leaving them unnoticed. For *Chaperina fusca* and *Kalophrynus pleurostigma*, their absence in Mt. Hamiguitan could be more of a combined effect of good camouflage and refuge in thick leaf litter conditions which were evident in Mt. Hamiguitan. It was also observed that during the capture of forest floor dependent species such as *Platymantis corrugata* and *Megophrys stejnegeri* samples have almost the same color with that of the leaf litter. But because of their larger size and their movement, their presence was noticed resulting to the capture of individual samples. For *Philautus cf poecilus* and *Limnectes cf diautus* which are endemic to mountain ranges found within Eastern Mindanao (Alcala and Brown 1998; Brown and Alcala 1977), their absence in Mt. Sinaka was almost expected.

The variability of microhabitats from which samples were found possibly relay that frogs use multiple microhabitats for survival. Various frog inventories in other Philippine islands also attest to different microhabitats from which anuran samples were documented (Diesmos *et al.* 2003; Alcala *et al.* 1997). These microhabitats are assumed to function as breeding areas, foraging and refuge sites during unwanted instances. For instance, *Ansonia muelleri* which was sampled in two differing microhabitats (ground and riparian) exhibited the use of varying microhabitats for survival. In previous records, adults were sampled on both forest duff and mountain streams (Alcala and Brown 1998; Inger 1954). Here, it appeared that forest streams are used mainly for breeding but the usual habitat is the forest duff. However, based on adult morphology (broadly webbed toes) and the presence of aquatic insects in the gut (Inger 1954) may nullify the statement above. Use of forest duff can be an opportunistic search for

food as competition is high in streams especially as gathered from our observation where three more species were found in the same stream, possibly depending also on the insects present in it. Another variation which was observed for *Platymantis guentheri* conform Alcala and Brown's (1998) report that this species is both terrestrial and arboreal. Being terrestrial, it was found on forest duff and low vegetation. Finding individuals of this species on both arboreal and ground microhabitats is then something not new.

The availability of water bodies needed by direct developers to complete the life cycle and the accompanying competition with other species may possibly push other species to utilize other microhabitats. In this study, the differences in the microhabitats to which *Rana grandocula* and *R. everetti* were sampled may support our assumption.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The Philippine anuran diversity is indeed rich and the data presented here qualifies to support this claim. Differing mountain ranges with dissimilar location and environmental conditions cater to diverse frog species and prominent dissimilarities in species composition are thus revealed. Frog species also occupy various microhabitats as exemplified by select field observations and literature. However, the data generated from this study can not strongly designate each microhabitat to a specific purpose. Even so, such overlaps in microhabitat use magnify the importance of even the smallest microhabitat in a forest. The alteration and/or destruction of these microhabitats would be direct threat to our frog species. Therefore the conservation not only of the forest itself but also of the microhabitats therein is an essential and timely concern.

Implication to Conservation. The data presented here supports the need of amphibian species to be able to utilize differing and many available microhabitats in order to survive and sustain their future generations. The complexity of available microhabitats in a forest, given their natural setting, is thus of good importance. Unfortunately, the significance of preserving these microhabitats has not been given the needed support in various current conservation efforts. It is then on this light that this paper raised the vital services that microhabitats provide for frogs and many other species and how such must therefore be included and somehow highlighted in future conservation efforts or in the review of current efforts to conserve the remaining forests of the country.

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